

Rapid Reviews Infectious Diseases

Review 1: "Genomic Epidemiology Uncovers the Timing and Origin of the Emergence of Mpox in Humans"

Jonas Michel Wolf¹

¹Hospital Moinhos de Vento

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RRID Evidence Scale rating by reviewer:

- **Reliable.** The main study claims are generally justified by its methods and data. The results and conclusions are likely to be similar to the hypothetical ideal study. There are some minor caveats or limitations, but they would/do not change the major claims of the study. The study provides sufficient strength of evidence on its own that its main claims should be considered actionable, with some room for future revision.

Review:**Introduction:**

The article presents a significant investigation into the emergence and transmission dynamics of the mpox virus (MPXV) in Nigeria, particularly in the context of the recent global outbreak. By generating and analyzing 112 MPXV genomes collected from 2021 to 2023, the study provides essential insights into the virus's origin, evolutionary mechanisms, and implications for public health. It identifies key aspects of the transmission lineage, pinpointing its emergence around July 2014 and its persistence in Southern Nigeria. This review will highlight the study's strengths, including its methodological rigor and relevance to public health, while also identifying opportunities for improvement, particularly in data interpretation and broader implications for surveillance and response strategies.

Strengths:

One of the standout strengths of this article is its contribution to the genomic understanding of MPXV, particularly in a region where data has been historically sparse. By generating 112 genomes, the study fills a crucial gap in the knowledge surrounding the virus's evolution and transmission. This large dataset enhances the reliability of the findings and allows for more robust phylogenetic analysis. The identification of the closest zoonotic outgroup to the human epidemic is particularly noteworthy, as it aids in understanding the zoonotic origins of the virus and the potential for future spillover events.

Moreover, the study's use of advanced analytical techniques, such as Bayesian phylogenetics via the Delphy tool, showcases an innovative approach to outbreak analytics. The ability to conduct near-real-time analysis is vital for rapid response in public health contexts, especially during emerging infectious disease outbreaks. This methodological advancement can be pivotal for epidemiologists and public health officials aiming to track the evolution of pathogens in real time.

Additionally, the study effectively contextualizes the findings within the broader timeline of the mpox epidemic, emphasizing the cryptic circulation of the virus before it was formally identified. This aspect highlights the importance of continuous surveillance and early detection, making the study relevant not only for understanding past events but also for informing future public health strategies.

Opportunities for Improvement:

Despite its strengths, the article has several areas that could benefit from enhancement. One notable opportunity for improvement lies in the discussion of the broader implications of the findings. While the study emphasizes the need for improved pathogen surveillance, it could further elaborate on specific strategies for enhancing surveillance systems in Nigeria and similar regions. For instance, discussing how community engagement, training for local healthcare workers, and the integration of genomic surveillance into existing public health frameworks could provide actionable insights for policymakers.

Furthermore, while the article mentions the role of APOBEC3 activity in increasing MPXV's evolutionary rate, it could delve deeper into the implications of this finding. Understanding the molecular mechanisms that drive the virus's adaptability could have significant ramifications for vaccine development and therapeutic interventions. A more detailed exploration of these aspects would enrich the discussion and offer valuable insights for future research directions.

Additionally, the article would benefit from a more comprehensive examination of the socio-economic factors influencing the spread of MPXV in Nigeria. Addressing how factors such as healthcare access, cultural practices, and community awareness contribute to the dynamics of the outbreak could provide a more holistic understanding of the challenges faced in managing the epidemic.

Lastly, while the study provides valuable genomic data, it could incorporate ecological and epidemiological factors that may have influenced the transmission dynamics of MPXV. For example, analyzing environmental conditions, wildlife interactions, and human behaviors could offer a more nuanced picture of the factors that contributed to the emergence and persistence of the virus in the region.

Conclusion:

In conclusion, the article significantly advances our understanding of the mpox virus's emergence and transmission in Nigeria. Its strengths lie in the robust genomic analysis and innovative use of phylogenetic tools, making it a critical contribution to the field. However, there are opportunities for improvement, particularly in discussing actionable public health strategies, exploring molecular implications, and considering socio-economic and ecological factors. By addressing these areas, future research can build upon these findings to inform effective surveillance and response efforts, ultimately contributing to the prevention of future outbreaks.